

THE ANALYSIS OF THE LITERARY TEXT INCLUDES THE PRINCIPLES THAT GUIDE IT AND EXPLAINS ITS MEANING

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ABSTRACT

The status of the text as a unit of speech above other units began to be scientifically recognized in the middle of the twentieth century. Today, text linguistics is a part of the civilization of scientific thought. Linguistics of text analysis can cover areas specific to the anthropocentric system. Therefore, the linguistics of literary texts has a great influence on the study of any language. The article discusses the urgency of this issue. The analysis of the literary text includes the principles that guide it and explains its meaning.

The search for text analysis, including the study of literary texts, gained new momentum, and the directions of text research began to be internalized. Text linguistics is the study of psycholinguistics, cognitive linguistics, gender linguistics, ethnolinguistics, functional grammar, and cognitive linguistics, etc. supplemented with comprehensive research. New trends in the development of modern linguistic scientific thinking - expansionism (the emergence of new "dual" sciences through the intersection of several sciences) and anthropocentrism (aimed at comprehensive recognition of the "person in the language"), functionalism (aimed at studying the use of language, the meaning of use) and became the object of exploratory research.

A text is a place where all levels of language - from sound to sentence - function. However, the text should not be considered

as a service environment, context only for other language units. It is also not just a concept related to one area of linguistics, such as syntax, but it is a complex unit of speech that can be recognized through comprehensive and in-depth, complex analysis. In this regard, the method of text analysis has become more complicated as "the highest and most multifaceted dynamic unit of speech, interconnected in terms of information, structure, and communication."

In the second half of the twentieth century, works on text theory began to appear. I.R. Galperin considered the text as an object of linguistic research. T.M. Nikolaeva showed two directions, formed by the peculiarities of text linguistics:

1) the direction that represents and analyzes the correctness of the text structure, and thus the correctness of communication;

2) to reveal the deep semantic aspects of a particular text.

That is, the necessary tools and principles for text analysis are provided. T.M. According to Dridze, "text is a unit of communication, the structure of meaningful information for communication and a defined method of organizing meaning, the implementation of reasoned and purposeful intelligent and thoughtful actions of the person, the desire to exchange material and practical interaction with other people and the analysis of linguistic and semiotic products".

I.R. Galperin himself said that the main character of the text is complete and has a title. However, some texts (lyrics, media text) may not have a title. Defines the text, expressing the views and opinions of foreign scholars on linguistic tools. I.R. Galperin considers: "A text is a purposeful and pragmatic device, combining different types of lexical, grammatical, logical, stylistic connections, with a literary connection to the document and a corresponding theme, with a complete idea, a speech". We learned from this definition that there is a parameter called speech, that is, it includes oral speech on paper. We know that speaking is a movement. And the text is not an unprepared speech, but a constant process of pre-recorded on paper, following the rules of language units. He also showed the dual nature of the text - static and moving sides. If we break it down, if it is described in turn in different units, then there are signs of immobility (implicit). If the text is produced (read), the message is re-encoded. In this case, if the above is the first, the second is the semantic code, the combination of nouns that occur to understand the text, and the third is the

culture code. Provides the necessary information from the culture of that time, the fourth - the hermeneutic code, a formulated set of tasks and answers in the message, the fifth - a symbolic code, the internal psychological causes of closed summary messages.

Linguistic analysis of a literary text has its principles. The history of Uzbek prose is deep, so it is necessary to take into account the internal and external factors of the selected text. There are many problems in the process of level learning of the Uzbek language through the text. Special principles should be taken into account in the prevention of such problems. The analysis of the literary text is guided by the following principles:

- Historical principle
- Social cognitive principle
- The principle of determining the individual style of the author
- Functional principle
- Conceptual, semantic position
- The principle of guiding the relationship between author and character categories
- The principle of unity of content and form. Historical position.

In the analysis of the works of some authors, the authors focus on the history and meaning of words whose meaning is not clear. It is especially noticeable in the analysis of the poems of M. Utemisov, and Abay Kunanbayev. This is because the epoch of poets' lives requires the interpretation of such obscure words in their works. For example, M. Utemisuly's "kalykpandai", "tarpandai", "kerisken", "bulan", "kyrkarlanu" and others. the semantics of many words are analyzed. In addition, the poet's use of solemn, motto, and meaningful, solemn words was especially interesting. In connection with

this principle, the authors are also guided by the socio-cognitive principle. This means not only describing the environment in which poets and writers lived, but also the meaning of words that reflect the values of that environment. Focuses on their social significance. For example, "zakunchik", "season", "applicant", "pesky", etc. The principle of determining the individual style of the author. Any work reflects the creative nature of its author, so the ability to visually test the language skills of the author through the work requires special care. At the same time, the purpose of the analysis in the textbook is clear, the examples are vivid. The author pays special attention to finding new uses and identifying the author's contribution to the literary language, and his achievements in the language. For example, the use of words in Abay's works, such as "feeding science", "finding science", "searching for science", "reading science", and "brainwashing" are examples that clearly show the author's individuality.

Functional principle.

In the analysis of the work, the authors consider the meaning of language units in terms of their function in a particular context, in that context. Functionally, each language unit at the language level, which is the basis for the linguistic organization of the text, is analyzed. The use of lexical units, grammatical entities, and sounds is considered in the functional aspect. Conceptual, semantic principles. Linguistic units are analyzed not only for documentary purposes, each analysis is associated with the author's conceptual artistic point of view.

Emphasizes the meaning conveyed outside the text through the background of the text. Attention is paid to visible information and

invisible, figurative information arising from the text and the language units that convey it. The principle of guiding the relationship between the categories of author-character. According to this principle, the types of narration in prose works, the image of the author, and the stylistics of the language units that give the foreign word are analyzed. While B. Mailin's "Bloody Revenge" is characterized by the words of the protagonist, the style of narration is based on real linguistic data, the novel "The Sign of Shuga", which today has become a classic example of Kazakh prose, has become a special object of analysis in terms of the author's image.

The principle of unity of content and form. In general, this principle is the basis of almost all principles. Because linguistic analysis is based on linguistic data, linguistic data is only the outer layer of content. In interpreting the linguistic data, the authors pay special attention not only to its external linguistic form but also to its relation to the content of the whole work, to the context, and the internal meaning of the work.

The development of text linguistics was the basis for the emergence of new directions, new approaches, new concepts, and new perspectives. Many monographs and articles have been published in this area, textbooks have been written, and conferences and symposiums have been held. P. Hartmann, a German journalist who has achieved many results in the theory of text, wrote in one of his works: "Today there is a linguistics based on the study of the text. This branch of linguistics is the most productive branch of linguistic research. It expands the range of interests in linguistics and opens the way to a collection of linguistic opinions. The study

of this new branch of linguistics was a new beginning of linguistic research".

Founded in the second half of the twentieth century, text linguistics is a branch of science that emerged at the intersection of several sciences. It ranges from traditional stylistics, which characterizes the art of language, to cognitive linguistics, which leads to human cognition, to philosophy.

Modern education is based on a new paradigm of education - from "viable" knowledge to the idea of "lifelong" education, based on scientific-cognitive, exploratory, creative activities in the formation of the individual.

Therefore, education is a priority, influencing the psychology of the

individual. And the connection of psychology with linguistics is psycholinguistics, in the aspect of which the theory of knowledge is considered. Cognition is formed by listening, recognizing, understanding, and seeing. Such comprehensive competence can be instilled in an individual through the method of text analysis in linguistics. Today's topical issue is a special consideration of methodological approaches to teaching all disciplines in connection with changes in the content, form, and structure of education.

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